

Thermodynamics of Bromoform and Ethanol Mixtures

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Manuscript received 25 May 1979, revised 6 February 1980, accepted 31 March 1980

Heats of mixing and vapour pressures of bromoform (A) + ethanol (B) as a function of concentration have been determined at 303.15 K. The excess Gibbs free energy of mixing, G^E values have been obtained from the measured vapour pressure data. The heats of mixing, H^E and G^E values are positive throughout the entire bromoform concentration range and $G^E > H^E$. The results have been analysed in terms of Barker and ideal associated model theory of non-electrolyte solutions. The analysis have revealed that both Barker theory and the ideal associated model approach [which here assumes the presence of $A_m B$ ($m=1, 2$), AB_k ($k=2$) and B_1 ($l=1$) molecular species] well describe the general behaviour of H^E with X_A over the entire bromoform concentration range for this mixture. The equilibrium constants for the various association reactions alongwith the enthalpy of formation of the various molecular species have also been calculated.

FOLLOWING Frank and Wen's model¹ of liquid water, it was believed that alcohols should also possess a similar type of cooperativity in the formation of hydrogen-bonded polymers. But there is considerable disagreement as to the identity of the predominant associated species²⁻⁶. Again while the solution hetero-associated data^{7,8} have been limited to calculation of equilibrium constants for 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 complexes only, Tucker and Christian⁹ have interpreted the results for their distribution studies to indicate that lower alkanols contain monomers, dimers and higher r-mers. The present work describes interactions in bromoform + ethanol mixtures.

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

Analytical grade ethanol (B.D.H) and bromoform (E. Merck A.R.) were purified in the manner suggested by Vogel¹⁰. The purity of the final samples was checked by density determinations at $298.15 \pm 0.01K$ which agreed to within $0.00005 \text{ g. ml}^{-1}$ with the literature values^{11,12}.

Heats of mixing measurements at $303.15 \pm 0.01K$ were made in an adiabatic calorimeter described elsewhere¹³. The performance of the calorimeter was tested by determining the heats of mixing of benzene and cyclohexane at $298.15 \pm 0.01K$ and

these agreed to within 0.3 percent (over the central range of concentration) with the corresponding literature values¹⁴.

Vapour pressures of bromoform + ethanol mixtures were determined by a static method in the manner described previously¹⁵. All vapour pressure measurements were reproducible to better than ± 0.02 torr.

The measured vapour pressure (78.12 torr) of ethanol at 303.15K agreed within 0.1 per cent with that (78.30 torr) at 303.15K obtained by Ferguson *et al*¹⁶. We are unaware of any vapour pressure data at 303.15K with which to compare our measured vapour pressure of bromoform.

Results

The molar heats of mixing H^E , and the measured vapour pressure data at 303.15K for bromoform + ethanol are recorded in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The H^E, G^E and TS^E data are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2.

The H^E data (Table 1) were fitted to the expression

$$\frac{H^E}{X_A(1-X_A)} = [h_0 + h_1(2X_A - 1) + h_2(2X_A - 1)^2] \dots \quad (1)$$

where X_A is the mole fraction of bromoform. The parameters h_0, h_1 and h_2 evaluated by fitting

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TABLE 1 — MEASURED MOLAR HEATS OF MIXING FOR DIFFERENT MOLE FRACTIONS X_A OF BROMOFORM AT 303.15 K

X_A	$H^E/J \text{ mol}^{-1}$	X_A	$H^E/J \text{ mol}^{-1}$
		Bromoform (A) + ethanol (B)	
0.1197	-43.08	0.5399	506.64
0.1501	-30.47	0.5801	558.71
0.2250	34.13	0.6353	611.58
0.2703	90.88	0.6850	639.75
0.3398	191.43	0.7503	634.99
0.4100	306.23	0.7852	610.47
0.4552	381.45	0.8201	568.29
0.4902	435.00	0.8950	413.35

TABLE 2 — MEASURED TOTAL VAPOUR PRESSURE, P ; ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT, γ ; RESIDUAL VAPOUR PRESSURE $R = P_{\text{exptl}} - P_{\text{calc}}$; MOLAR EXCESS GIBBS FREE ENERGIES, G^E ; AND TS^E FOR DIFFERENT MOLE FRACTIONS X_A OF BROMOFORM AT 303.15 K

X_A	P/Torr	γ_A	γ_B	P_A/Torr	P_B/Torr	$R = P_{\text{exptl}} - P_{\text{calc}}$	$G^E/J \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$TS^E/J \text{ mol}^{-1}$
				Bromoform(A) + ethanol (B)				
0.0000	78.21	3.5589	1.0000	0.00	78.21	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.0903	73.99	2.8552	1.0088	2.39	71.76	-0.16	261.96	-306.40
0.1502	71.56	2.5354	1.0241	3.53	68.04	-0.01	408.49	-436.68
0.2750	66.53	2.0684	1.0813	5.27	61.28	-0.02	651.77	-557.61
0.3697	63.17	1.8127	1.1530	6.21	56.80	0.15	782.83	-544.92
0.4503	60.15	1.6323	1.2419	6.80	53.35	-0.00	856.65	-486.20
0.5300	57.43	1.4773	1.3675	7.25	50.22	-0.04	892.22	-397.51
0.6601	53.17	1.2665	1.7138	7.73	45.51	-0.07	857.22	-226.91
0.7799	48.68	1.1201	2.3524	8.08	40.44	0.15	700.71	-83.09
0.8402	44.54	1.0660	2.9137	8.28	36.36	-0.10	567.60	-29.28
0.9250	33.67	1.0155	4.2664	8.67	24.97	0.01	308.46	10.21
1.0000	9.21	1.0000	6.5812	9.21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Fig. 1. Enthalpies of Mixing H^E for Bromoform(1) + Ethanol(2) at 303.15 K, O, experimental H^E ; Δ , calculated H^E according to ideal associated model that assumes the presence of AB, AB_2 , A_2B and B molecular species; \square , calculated H^E according to ideal associated model that assumes the presence of AB, AB_2 , AB_3 and B molecular species ($K_{1,0.5} = 0.09$, $\Delta H_{AB} = -0.5 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$; $K_{0.5} = 0.04$, $\Delta H_B = 2.5 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$; $K_{1,1} = 0.7$, $\Delta H_{AB_2} = -1.15 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$; $K_{1,1.5} = 0.06$, $\Delta H_{AB_3} = -0.5 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$)

$H^E / X_A (1 - X_A)$ to expression (1) by the method of least squares are given together with the standard deviation of the molar heats of mixing, $\sigma(H^E)$ in Table 3.

The vapour pressure data were used to evaluate the molar excess Gibbs free energy, G^E , by Barker's

method¹⁷. The form of the function used for G^E , following Redlich Kister¹⁸ as

$$G^E / RT = X_A (1 - X_A) [G_0 + G_1(2X_A - 1) + G_2(2X_A - 1)^2 + G_3(2X_A - 1)^3] \dots \quad (2)$$

where G_0 , G_1 , G_2 and G_3 are adjustable parameters.

Fig. 2. Excess functions for bromoform (A) + ethanol (B) at 303.15 K \odot , G^E ; and \triangle , TS^E

These parameters are recorded in Table 3. The second virial coefficients of ethanol were evaluated from the Berthelot relation¹⁹ using critical constant data^{20,21}. The critical constants, V_c , P_c and T_c of bromoform were evaluated from the Lyderson method, the Riedel method and the modified Guldberg rule, respectively as reported²⁰. The cross virial coefficients were taken as $(B_{11} + B_{22})/2$. The thermodynamic consistency of the data were tested¹⁸ by plotting in (γ_A / γ_B) versus x_A . The positive and negative areas bounded by the curve $\ln(\gamma_A / \gamma_B)$ versus x_A and the X-axis agreed to better than 0.2 percent.

curve of TS^E against X_{ethanol} is highly unsymmetrical about X_{ethanol} .

At the simplest qualitative level the observed H^E data for this mixture may be accounted for if we assume that (i) ethanol is self-associated and there is a change (decrease) in its self-association when it is mixed with bromoform, (ii) there is a hydrogen-bonded interaction between the hydroxyl oxygen of ethanol and the bromoform hydrogen and (iii) there is specific interaction between the hydroxyl hydrogen of ethanol with the bromine of bromoform. The negative values of H^E for high ethanol concentrations are

TABLE 3—PARAMETERS X_m ($X=h$ OR G) OF EQUATIONS 1 AND 2, STANDARD DEVIATION OF PRESSURE $\sigma(P)$ ALONG WITH THE STANDARD DEVIATION OF H^E , $\sigma(H^E)$ FOR BROMOFORM (A) + ETHANOL (B) MIXTURE AT 303.15 K

m	0	1	2	3	$\sigma(H^E)/J \text{ mol}^{-1}$	$\sigma(P)/\text{Torr}$
h_m	1801.00	3067.84	255.79	-	2.38	-
G_m	1.4021	0.3073	0.1556	-0.0190	-	0.12

Discussion

We are unaware of any H^E or G^E data for bromoform + ethanol with which to compare our results.

Heats of mixing for bromoform (A) + ethanol (B) are negative for solution rich in ethanol but they become positive for solutions rich in bromoform. The S-shaped H^E curve attains a maximum negative value of 45 J mol^{-1} at $X_{\text{ethanol}} = 0.90$ and maximum positive value of 640 J mol^{-1} at $X_{\text{ethanol}} = 0.29$. Further TS^E is negative at all the ethanol mole fractions (except for $X_{\text{ethanol}} = 0.075$) for which the experimental data are available and the

then due essentially to the factor (ii). This is because while interactions due to the factor(ii) can occur without breaking the alcohol-alcohol hydrogen bond, the same is not true of interactions due to factor(iii). Again in the hydrogen bonded interaction due to factor(ii) limits the orientational freedom of the bromoform molecules thus making TS^E strongly negative so that G^E should be (as indeed is) positive. The positive values of H^E at high bromoform concentrations are due to the rupture of alcohol-alcohol hydrogen bonds followed by their subsequent hydrogen-bonded interaction with bromoform molecules. This in turn would require the TS^E at high bromoform concentrations to be considerably more positive than that at low bromoform concentrations and thus explains

the unsymmetrical nature of TSE^E versus $X_{\text{bromoform}}$ curve.

We examined our results using Barker's theory²². It was assumed that bromoform (A) and ethanol (B) have the following geometrical parameters :

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Lattice } z = 4 \\ &\text{Bromoform molecules (A)} \\ &r_A = 3 \quad Q_R^{A'} = 1 \quad Q_R^{A''} = 7 \\ &\text{Ethanol molecules (B)} \\ &r_B = 2 \quad Q_O^B = 2 \quad Q_H^B = 1 \quad Q_B^B = 3 \end{aligned}$$

where O, H and R respectively, hydroxyl oxygen, hydrogen and hydrocarbon surface of ethanol, and H' and R' represent the hydrogen and bromine surface of bromoform. The interactions first considered were a specific (OH') interaction of strength U_3 between the hydroxyl oxygen of ethanol and the hydrogen of bromoform, a specific (O.....H) interaction of strength U_2 between the hydroxyl oxygen and hydroxyl hydrogen of ethanol and a non-specific interaction for all the remaining contact points. For the sake of simplicity these non-specific interactions for all the remaining contact points were considered to have the same strength U_1 . Excess energy of mixing at constant volume U_V^E , values at $X_A = 0.3, 0.5$ and 0.7 were then calculated²² from this theory and they did not reproduce the experimental H^E values. (It is customary while testing a lattice theory to convert U_V^E values to measurements at constant pressure, H^E , using the relation $U_V^E = H^E - TV^E \alpha_m / (K_T)_m$ where α_m , $(K_T)_m$ and V^E are respectively the expansivity, isothermal compressibility and excess volume of the mixture. However, since V^E is small (V^E for an equimolar mixture is $0.180 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), contribution of $TV^E \alpha_m / (K_T)_m$ term would be negligibly small and for the present analysis we have assumed $U_V^E \approx H^E$. The best values of U_1, U_2, U_3 (designated as $U_i^{(1)}$ ($i = 1$ to 3) and the corresponding H^E values designated as $H^E(1)$ are recorded in Table 4.

We next considered a slightly different model in which in addition to the above interaction, one of the bromines of bromoform was assumed to be involved in a specific (H...Br) interaction of strength U_4 with the hydroxyl hydrogen of ethanol. The bromoform was considered to have the following $Q_R^{A'} = 6$. The agreement between the theoretical²² and the experimental H^E values is now better as compared to the earlier one although it still is by no means quantitative. (The values of U_i ($i = 1$ to 4) and H^E are designated as $U_i^{(2)}$ and $H^E(2)$ in Table 4).

The interaction energies and the H^E and G^E values at $X_A = 0.3, 0.5$ and 0.7 calculated from this theory are recorded in Table 4, and they compare reasonably well with the corresponding experimental values. The theoretical results thus show similar qualitative behaviour to that shown by the experimental data. Models of bromoform molecules with two and three hydrogen contact points were also considered but they did not give better results. Perhaps associated complexes of the general formula $A_l B_j$ and B_n are present in these mixtures. H^E and G^E data for this mixture were then analysed in terms of the ideal associated model^{23,24} which assumed that in a binary solution of bromoform (A) and ethanol (designated as B_n since ethanol is self-associated) mutual equilibrium of the species $A_m B, AB_k$ and B_l ($l = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 1$; $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$; $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$; $m = 2, 3, \dots, m$) exist according to the reactions

so that the equilibrium constants for the various association reactions represented by equation (3) are

$$K_{m,1} = \frac{a_{A_m B}}{a_A^m a_{B_n}^1} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$K_{1,k} = \frac{a_{AB_k}}{a_A a_{B_n}^{k/n}} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{and } K_{l/n} = \frac{a_{B_l}}{a_{B_n}^{1/n}} \quad \dots (6)$$

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF H^E AND G^E VALUES CALCULATED ACCORDING TO BARKER'S THEORY WITH VALUES INTERPOLATED FROM THE MEASURED VALUES AT THREE MOLE FRACTIONS OF THE COMPONENT (A) AND THE INTERACTION ENERGIES OF BROMOFORM (A) + ETHANOL (B) AT 303.15 K

Property/ $J \text{ mol}^{-1}$	The mole fraction of the component (A)			Interaction energies/ $J \text{ mol}^{-1}$	
	0.3	0.5	0.7		
H_{exptl}^E	130.00	450.00	640.00		
$H^{E(1)}$	426.73	653.04	564.27	$U_1^{(1)} = 322.3,$	$U_3^{(1)} = -2309.48, U_4^{(1)} = -1987.35$
$H^{E(2)}$	353.77	444.86	292.38	$U_1^{(2)} = 161.36,$	$U_2^{(2)} = -2309.48; U_3^{(2)} = -1987.35; U_4^{(2)} = -1618.18$
G_{exptl}^E	690.00	882.00	810.00		
$G^{E(2)}$	400.75	455.35	531.70		

TABLE 5—THE EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS (MOLE FRACTION SCALE) FOR THE VARIOUS COMPLEXING REACTIONS TOGETHER WITH THE ENTHALPIES OF FORMATION OF VARIOUS MOLECULAR SPECIES AND THE VARIANCE OF THE FIT σ_D^2 AT 303.15 K

Equilibrium constants	Reaction of bromoform with ethanol	Parameter	Mixtures of ethanol(B) with bromoform (A)
$K_{1,0.5}$	0.10	$\Delta H_{AB}/\text{KJ mol}^{-1}$	-0.50
$K_{2,0.5}$	0.05	$\Delta H_{A_2B}/\text{KJ mol}^{-1}$	-0.50
$K_{1,1}$	0.80	$\Delta H_{AB_2}/\text{KJ mol}^{-1}$	-1.15
$K_{0.5}$	0.04	$\Delta H_B/\text{KJ mol}^{-1}$	2.50
		σD_{10}^2	0.016
		σD_{11}^2	0.019

where 'a' denotes activities in the manner described previously²⁵. The analysis of the activity coefficient data suggests that these mixtures may be assumed to have either AB, A₂B, AB₂ and B or AB, AB₂, AB₃ and B molecular species in solution. We next considered our H^E data in the manner described earlier²⁵.

Examination of the H^E data of this mixture in terms of models that involved consideration of

- i) AB, A₂B, AB₂ and B, and
- ii) AB, AB₂, AB₃ and B molecular species.

Using the various K values for a solution containing AB, A₂B, AB₂ and B species, we obtained²⁵ the various ΔH values which are recorded in Table 5. The calculated H^E values are plotted in fig. 1. It is evident from this fig. that the theoretical H^E values well describe the general behaviour of H^E with X_A for bromoform (A) + ethanol (B₂) mixture.

A similar process was applied to the case when the mixture contain AB_m (m = 1 to 3) and B molecular species. However, no values of ΔH_{AB_m} (m = 1 to 3) and ΔH_B could yield H^E values that described the experimental behaviour of H^E with X_A for this mixture. The calculated H^E values are either positive or negative throughout the entire bromoform concentration range. Further the quantitative agreement is also not good. (See Fig. 1 where only those ΔH_{AB_m} and ΔH_B values are considered that render H^E_{cacl} positive throughout the entire bromoform concentration range).

The analysis of H^E and activity coefficient data for bromoform + ethanol mixture thus suggests that this mixture is characterized by the presence of AB, AB₂, A₂B and B molecular species in solution.

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